

The Mobilising Effect of AI-Generated Misinformation: The Case of Slovakia

Cambridge Journal of Political
Affairs
Volume 6, Issue 1 (2025): 200-208
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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16632682
cambridgepoliticalaffairs.co.uk

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This paper investigates the role of AI-generated misinformation in shaping electoral outcomes, focusing on the 2023 Slovakian parliamentary elections and the rise of populist leader Robert Fico. Specifically, it examines whether the circulation of AI-generated audio, which falsely incriminated opposition leader Michal Šimečka of election fraud, influenced voter behaviour and contributed to Fico's electoral success. Despite the speculative and hypothetical nature of the analysis due to data constraints at the time of writing (in early 2024), the paper asserts that AI-generated misinformation played a key role in galvanising disenchanted voters and amplifying the "Trump effect," particularly in a highly contentious election. Drawing on existing literature, the paper underscores the growing influence of digital media and AI technologies in spreading misinformation, which can disrupt democratic processes. Lastly, the essay calls for further empirical research to shed light on the impact of AI-driven disinformation on electoral outcomes. This research contributes to the growing body of literature on misinformation in politics and the intersection of AI, populism, and electoral dynamics.

INTRODUCTION

The influence of technology and artificial intelligence (AI) on politics has recently become an important topic of discussion and research, particularly in understanding the dynamics of electoral processes in the digital age. A notable example of such influence occurred in the Slovak parliamentary elections in 2023. Forty-eight hours before Slovaks headed to the polls to vote for their new parliament and prime minister, two fake audios began circulating, incriminating Michal Šimečka, Progressive Slovakia (PS) leader, of election fraud. Then, on September 30, 2023, Robert Fico, the populist leader of Direction-Social Democracy (Smer-SD), became Slovakia's prime minister. At its core, this paper seeks to answer the question, "Does AI-generated misinformation contribute to the electoral success of populist leaders?" This study contends that Fico was able to mobilise voters in the 2023 parliamentary election through the "Trump effect" and that the fake audio mobilised his latent supporters who would not have voted for him without the emergence of the AI-generated audio. Due to data constraints and given that this is a recent and evolving topic, the paper is primarily exploratory and speculative, with the ultimate goal of contributing to the growing literature on misinformation and disinformation, specifically in the context of elections and the rise of populism worldwide.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Though the literature about the intersection of technology and politics is not extensive, a few key contributors helped shape this paper. Benkler, Faris, and Roberts (2018) provide a comprehensive analysis of network propaganda in American politics, highlighting the role of digital platforms in disseminating misinformation and fostering radicalisation. Their study underscores the ability of online networks to amplify populist narratives and manipulate public opinion, thereby influencing electoral outcomes. Though their focus is largely US-centric, the argument still holds in the Slovakian context. Next, Lenoir and Anderson (2023) build on this framework by discussing the evolving landscape of disinformation studies and its implications for understanding the post-truth era. Their work emphasises the need to examine the complex interplay between technology, media, and political discourse in shaping public perceptions.

Bergmann (2020) offers insights into the relationship between populism and misinformation, arguing that populist leaders often exploit grievances and fears to advance their political agendas. Bergmann's insights into this relationship are especially relevant to understanding how Fico mobilised supporters during the 2023 election. Indeed, with the rise of digital media, people are exposed to an onslaught of knowledge and

information, making it far more difficult to identify what is fact and what is fiction. This then leaves a gap for misinformation to rise and for the manipulation of democratic processes. Eksi (2021) extends this analysis by exploring the phenomenon of digital populism and its impact on the rise of right-wing populist movements. The study highlights how the internet serves as a fertile ground for populist mobilisation, allowing for the dissemination of divisive rhetoric and conspiracy theories.

Dusková (2023) provides valuable insights into the history of populism in Slovakia, as well as the geographic dynamics of populist voting patterns in Slovakia, offering a contextual understanding of the political landscape in which Fico's electoral success unfolded. Particularly, she explores regional disparities and their effects on voter behaviour. Her analysis highlights that support for populist leaders like Fico has been strongest in economically disadvantaged regions, typically located in the northern and eastern parts of the country (Dusková, 2023, p. 21). Unsurprisingly, Fico's nationalist rhetoric and focus on economic protectionism and opposition to Western liberal elites would appeal to the Slovakian population hit with lower wages, higher unemployment, and weaker infrastructure. This geographic divide reflects a broader political landscape that made it possible for Fico to return to a position of power. Slovakia's political culture has been shaped by distrust in traditional elites and scepticism toward EU integration. Fico capitalised on these sentiments by portraying himself as a defender of Slovak identity, and AI-generated misinformation simply reinforced existing anxieties within the population and intensified regional divides.

Hajdu et al. (2023) contribute to this discourse by presenting the findings of the GLOBSEC Trends 2023 report, which highlights the enduring appeal of populist rhetoric in the face of global challenges. The report underscores the resilience of populist narratives in shaping public opinion and mobilising support among disaffected voters, thus providing further insight into Fico's electoral strategy. Namely, the authors found that "53% in Slovakia fear that the elections taking place in September 2023 will be manipulated, a narrative often pushed by anti-establishment parties to fuel doubts about democratic processes in the country" (Hajdu et al., 2023, p. 79). Moreover, trust in the government declined from 30% in 2022 to 18% in 2023, and trust in the media was 37% (Hajdu et al., 2023, pp. 78, 80). Though these are only some of the statistics collected in the report, they point to an overall erosion of trust in the government, presenting an opportunity for Fico and populist narratives to sway public opinion and for these tensions to be exacerbated by the salience of AI.

Walker (2023) offers a comprehensive overview of the 2023 general election in Slovakia, contextualising Fico's electoral victory within the broader dynamics of coalition politics and shifting voter preferences. While his report does not discuss AI-generated misinformation, it is still useful for an introductory understanding of who the key candidates were, their political parties, and the overall political landscape leading up to the election.

Lastly, Karina V. Korostelina's (2016) *Trump Effect* discusses Donald Trump's rise and his appeal, underscoring the adeptness of populist leaders in exploiting societal divisions and capitalising on pre-existing anxieties. Her work will serve as the theoretical framework of this study. Though her focus is on the US and Trump, many of her findings are applicable across different political contexts, including Slovakia and Fico.

CONTEXT AND DEFINITIONS

Definitions

Before further delving into the subject matter, I will define the key concepts. While many definitions of populism and AI exist, the ones below are the ones I believe are best suited to this research.

Populism can be understood "as an ideology that considers society to be ultimately separated into two homogeneous and antagonistic groups, 'the pure people' versus 'the corrupt elite', and which argues that politics should be an expression of the *volonté générale* (general will) of the people" (Mudde, 2004, p. 543).

Meanwhile, artificial intelligence (AI) will be understood in this paper as "the theory and development of computer systems able to perform tasks that normally require human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation between languages" (Oxford Reference, n.d.).

Lastly, misinformation is the spread of false information, while disinformation is the purposeful spread of inaccurate information with the goal of misleading the target audience (American Psychological Association, n.d.).

Benefits and Pitfalls of AI

AI holds the potential to both strengthen and challenge democratic processes. On the one hand, AI can strengthen governance by improving public service delivery, enabling better decision-making through data analysis, and fostering more responsive citizen-government interactions (Duberry, 2021). This facilitation can, in theory, increase government efficiency by using data collected by AI algorithms to allocate resources better and address societal needs. On the other hand, AI also poses certain risks to democracy. First, the lack of transparency in AI decision-making processes can undermine accountability, making it difficult for citizens to understand or contest government actions (Manheim and Kaplan, 2021, p. 153). Additionally, algorithmic biases can lead to discriminatory outcomes, further entrenching existing structural inequalities (Manheim and Kaplan, 2021, p. 159). Second, the increasing sophistication of AI-generated misinformation and the rise of fake news in the past few years have exacerbated the erosion of public trust in the media (Manheim and Kaplan, 2021, pp. 150-152).

In electoral processes, AI-generated misinformation can fuel populist appeals in unprecedented ways, and understanding this dynamic is crucial for future elections. Though election hacking is not new, AI has amplified its scope and speed, making it easier for actors with malicious intent to manipulate public opinion (Manheim and Kaplan, 2021). As seen in recent elections worldwide, populists can leverage media, such as Trump's use of Twitter during his 2016 campaign and during the 2023 Slovakian election. Currently, governments do not have adequate tools to detect AI-generated disinformation, nor are experts able to catch up to the quickly evolving technological landscape. Furthermore, regulation has its loopholes and does not serve as an effective barrier (Meaker, 2023). While implementing strong regulatory frameworks is a necessary first step, investing in digital literacy and ensuring that AI is used ethically and inclusively are equally important. Overall, AI does have certain benefits and may be useful in boosting efficiency. Nevertheless, it poses threats to democratic electoral processes, especially when it becomes almost impossible to differentiate between what is fact and what is fiction.

Historical Context

In Slovakia, the history of populism is deeply intertwined with the country's transition from communism to democracy and its subsequent socioeconomic transformations. Following the Velvet Revolution in 1989, which peacefully ended communist rule, Slovakia embarked on a path toward liberal democracy and market-oriented reforms (Dusková, 2023, p. 4). However, the transition process was marked by economic challenges, social dislocation, and political turbulence, providing fertile ground for the emergence of populist movements. One of the defining figures in Slovakian populism is Vladimír Mečiar, who rose to prominence in the early 1990s as the leader of the Movement for a Democratic Slovakia (HZDS) (Dusková, 2023, p. 4). Mečiar's populist appeal was rooted in his charisma, anti-establishment rhetoric, and promises to protect Slovakian interests amid the uncertainties of the post-communist transition. (Deegan-Krause, 2012, p. 189). Under his leadership, Slovakia experienced a period of political instability characterised by authoritarian tendencies, corruption scandals, and economic stagnation (Dusková, 2023). Mečiar's brand of populism resonated with segments of the population who felt marginalised by the rapid pace of economic reforms and disillusioned with mainstream political parties (Deegan-Krause, 2012, p. 188). Many Slovaks, particularly those in rural areas and industrial regions, perceived themselves as being left behind in the transition to a market economy (Deegan-Krause, 2012, pp. 192-193). They felt disenfranchised by the perceived elitism and corruption of the political establishment, leading them to seek alternative voices that promised to address their grievances.

Robert Fico, the leader of Direction—Social Democracy (Smer-SD), emerged as a prominent populist figure in Slovakia in the early 2000s. Fico capitalised on similar sentiments of disenchantment with mainstream politics, positioning himself as a champion of the working class and defender of Slovakian sovereignty. His party's platform combined elements of social welfare policies with nationalist rhetoric, appealing to those who felt marginalised by globalisation and European integration (Mesežnikov et al., 2008). Disenfranchisement, in the context of populism, can be understood as a sense of political alienation, marginalisation, or exclusion experienced by certain segments of the population within a society manifesting through various forms, including feeling ignored or marginalised by political elites, perceiving a lack of representation or responsiveness in the political system, or experiencing economic, social, or cultural marginalisation (Chan et al., 2020, pp. 831-832; Margalit, 2019, pp. 159, 165).

Slovaks who feel disenfranchised may be more susceptible to voting for a populist like Robert Fico for several reasons. First, Fico's populist rhetoric often taps into nationalist sentiments and cultural identity, resonating with those who feel a sense of loss or displacement in the face of globalisation and multiculturalism. Second, Fico's promises of economic protectionism and social welfare measures offer a sense of security and stability to those who feel economically precarious or left behind by neoliberal reforms (Morris and Bauerova, 2023). Moreover, Fico's ability to navigate the complexities of the post-communist transition and present himself as a strong leader capable of standing up to external pressures has garnered him support among segments of the population who feel disempowered by the perceived influence of foreign entities and multinational corporations (Dlhopolec, 2023). By positioning himself firmly against external threats to Slovakian sovereignty, Fico taps into fears and anxieties about the loss of national identity and autonomy, a sentiment that has been successfully leveraged by other populists worldwide.

The history of populism in Slovakia is characterised by the emergence of charismatic leaders who capitalise on socioeconomic grievances and feelings of disenfranchisement among certain segments of the population. Slovaks who feel marginalised or left behind by economic reforms and political elites may be more susceptible to the appeals of populist leaders like Robert Fico, who promise to protect national interests and restore a sense of dignity and agency to the disempowered.

Structural Reasons for Populism

While this paper seeks to understand the role of AI in populist electoral success, it also recognises that there are structural reasons for the rise of populist leaders. Among them are economic insecurity and distrust in democratic institutions. Indeed, economic hardship and inequality can fuel resentment against perceived elites and international institutions, while cultural and ideological divides deepen social fragmentation, making populist rhetoric more appealing. Moreover, declining trust in traditional political parties and institutions often leads voters to seek alternatives that promise change (Deegan-Krause, 2012; Haughton et al., 2025). In the current technological landscape, the spread of misinformation and disinformation, particularly through social media, further exacerbates these conditions, allowing populist leaders to manipulate public opinion and mobilise support (Benkler et al., 2018). In Slovakia, these structural factors played a significant role in Robert Fico's return to power in the 2023 parliamentary elections. Economic disparities between urban and rural regions and lingering frustrations over corruption and governance failures created an opening for Fico's populist-nationalist messaging (Dusková, 2023; Kevický, 2022). His campaign harnessed public scepticism toward Western institutions and liberal democratic values, positioning him as a defender of Slovak identity. The fragmented media environment, which has been increasingly vulnerable to misinformation and disinformation, further aided his success. By exploiting these structural vulnerabilities, Fico was able to consolidate support among disaffected voters and re-establish himself as a viable candidate during the election.

The 2023 Parliamentary Election

Between 2019 and 2024, Slovakia had four prime ministers in power. In late 2022, following a vote of no-confidence, a snap election was called, in which two prominent figures emerged as central players in the parliamentary elections: Robert Fico and Michal Šimečka (Walker, 2023, p. 4). Fico, a seasoned politician, had served as Prime Minister of Slovakia multiple times and was the leader of the Smer-SD party, known for its centre-left policies. On the other hand, Michal Šimečka represented a new wave of politics in Slovakia. As a member of the PS party, Šimečka advocated for liberal democratic values, transparency, and European integration (Walker, 2023, p. 7). He attracted support from younger demographics and urban intellectuals seeking progressive change in Slovakian governance (Spectator staff, Dlhopolec, and Terenzani, 2023).

The main competing parties in Slovakia's parliament, Smer-SD and PS, presented voters with a clear ideological divide. Smer-SD, under Fico's leadership, positioned itself as a defender of traditional Slovakian values and interests, often advocating for a strong state role in the economy and a cautious approach to European integration (Walker, 2023, p. 8). Meanwhile, PS championed liberal democratic principles, promoting individual rights, anti-corruption measures, and a pro-European stance (Walker, 2023, p. 7). This ideological clash reflected broader societal divisions within Slovakia, between those favouring continuity with the past and those advocating for progressive change.

Key events leading up to the 2023 election exacerbated pre-existing tensions and provided the opportunity for Fico to make his return on the political stage. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed significant weaknesses

in the Slovak healthcare system and governance structure, contributing to widespread frustration (Haughton et al., 2025, p. 10). These frustrations, compounded by the government responses and intra-coalition conflicts during the pandemic, created fertile ground for populist messaging. Additionally, the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 played a key role insofar as it allowed Fico to exploit anxieties about rising energy prices, economic insecurity, and war fatigue to push scepticism toward the West and NATO (Haughton et al., 2025, p. 11). His pro-Russian and anti-sanction rhetoric resonated particularly in more rural and economically vulnerable regions. Thus, Fico stepped in and presented himself as a symbol of stability and unity for the country.

In the elections, Smer-SD won 23% of the votes, nearly five percentage points more than predicted in opinion polls, with PS trailing behind at 18% (Spectator staff, Dlhopolec, and Terenzani, 2023). Regarding the vote distribution, Slovaks living abroad and in the Bratislava region (the largest urban centre) voted for more liberal parties like PS, and the remaining seven regions voted for more right and radical right-leaning parties like Smer-SD (Spectator staff, Dlhopolec, and Terenzani, 2023). These results confirm the trends that Dusková (2023) and Kevický (2022) outline in their respective papers. They support Kevický's (2022) claim that radical right parties have strong support in the left-behind and rural regions and weak support in urban areas (Kevický, 2022, p. 15-16), thus aligning with the central argument that Fico was able to mobilise his voter base by tapping into nationalist sentiments and targeting the disenfranchised part of the population.

The 2023 parliamentary elections in Slovakia were highly contentious, marked by intense political polarisation and allegations of misinformation campaigns. As in many other countries, social media and digital platforms have become increasingly significant in shaping public opinion (Bergmann, 2020, p. 262). As discussed by Bergmann (2020), the digitalisation of media "has enabled those with conspiratorial tendencies to bypass the previously powerful gatekeepers of the mainstream media" (Bergmann, 2020, p. 262). Moreover, the change in the way we consume media has brought about a saturation of indiscriminate information, making it much more difficult for people to discern between what is and is not true (Bergmann, 2020, p. 252). In this vein, Fico has taken advantage of social media and Slovaks' vulnerability to mis- and disinformation to mobilise voters. Particularly, Fico and Šimečka's opponents were able to leverage the fake audio that first appeared on Telegram (a barely regulated messaging app) two days before Slovakia's parliamentary elections and before spreading on TikTok, YouTube, and Facebook, especially because it was the moratorium period and Šimečka could not directly address Slovaks to defend himself (Devine et al., 2024). More surprising, however, is people's support of Fico, especially given the reason behind his resignation from office in 2018, following the murder of an investigative journalist and his fiancée in their home (Morris and Bauerova, 2023; Walker, 2023, pp. 8-9). The journalist was looking into corruption claims about Fico and his entourage. Thus, how was Fico able to mobilise such a strong voter base, given the corruption claims from his past and the Slovaks' distrust of the government?

Theoretical Framework – The "Trump Effect"

Karina V. Korostelina's (2016) *Trump Effect* discusses Donald Trump's rise to popularity and appeal among voters. In her book, she argues that Trump's success is based on three main pillars:

1. National Identity: Trump champions a specific vision of American national identity centred around making America great again, which resonates with his supporters (Korostelina, 2016, p. 2). He defines the boundaries of social groups and their positions within the nation in a way that empowers his supporters.
2. Emotional mirroring: Trump connects with voters through mirrored emotions. He displays the same anger, frustration, and aggression as his supporters (Korostelina, 2016, p. 65). This provides a feeling of unity and resonates emotionally with voters. Trump justifies and encourages the retaliatory aggression of his supporters against those who oppose him.
3. Prioritisation of national interest: Trump promotes an agenda that prioritises the interests of American citizens over globalism and universal values (Korostelina, 2016, pp. 9, 116). He supports policies that restrict immigration and target groups like illegal Mexican immigrants and Muslims. This appeals to voters who feel left behind by globalisation and cultural changes.

Overall, the author argues that Trump has tapped into the grievances of voters who feel their needs have been ignored by the political establishment (Korostelina, 2016, pp. 8, 39). Through championing their identity, mirroring their emotions, and promoting policies they support, Trump has been able to gain popularity and mobilise voters. However, some of his tactics, such as insults, bullying, and aggression, have been criticised.

Applying The “Trump Effect” To Robert Fico

Robert Fico’s recent political resurgence and successful mobilisation of the Slovakian voter base can be understood through the “Trump effect” as outlined by Korostelina (2016). Similarly to Donald Trump in the United States, Fico capitalised on widespread discontent and disillusionment among certain segments of the population. While Slovakia has a different historical and political context, the emotional and symbolic dynamics identified by Korostelina are still applicable in this case. By positioning himself as a champion of the common people and tapping into grievances over issues such as immigration, globalisation, and economic inequality, Fico was able to galvanise support from disaffected voters who felt marginalised by mainstream political parties. Fico’s rhetoric also constructs a populist national identity that appeals to those voters to reinforce in-group solidarity. Moreover, the proliferation of AI-generated misinformation played into Fico’s strategy, allowing him to exploit existing fears and prejudices within society to his advantage. Not only does this tactic echo Trump’s strategy, but it also illustrates an evolution of the “Trump Effect” in the digital age, where populist emotional mirroring is now amplified by algorithms.

Additionally, Fico’s leadership style and persona bear resemblances to Trump’s approach, characterised by a charismatic and often polarising demeanour (Morris and Bauerova, 2023). His unapologetic stance on controversial issues and willingness to defy political norms resonated with a segment of the electorate disillusioned with the status quo. Additionally, Fico’s success can be attributed to his use of media and communication channels to disseminate his message and shape public perception. By leveraging social media platforms and employing populist rhetoric that resonated with ordinary citizens’ concerns, he cultivated a loyal base of supporters and generated momentum for his party despite the corruption claims against him.

Based on the previous sections outlining Fico’s rise to success and some of the main strategies he leverages to mobilise support, it would be interesting to determine if there is a causal relationship between the fake audio and voter preferences. The context and information given thus far point to the fact that Fico’s success can be understood through the main determinants of populism (immigration, culture, and economics). However, it is likely that in this highly contentious election, mis- and disinformation played a pivotal role in mobilising latent supporters. It is not new information that populists can leverage media to their advantage, but AI-generated mis- and disinformation can further exacerbate these effects. The research design proposed below is an attempt to capture this effect.

METHODOLOGY

For this paper, the research design and methodology will be explained in detail in this section. However, the experiment itself will not be conducted since the data is not available. Since this paper aims to answer the question, “Does AI-generated misinformation lead to the successful election of a populist?” by conducting a case study of Slovakia’s 2023 parliamentary elections, these are the null and alternative hypotheses to test:

- Null Hypothesis (H₀): The fake audio of Michal Šimečka had no effect on a disenfranchised respondent’s voting outcome.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): The fake audio of Michal Šimečka convinced disenfranchised respondents to vote for Fico.

First, a randomised controlled trial would be conducted to test the hypotheses. The experiment would involve two groups: one exposed to the fake audio (treatment group) and another not exposed (control group). The treatment group would be further stratified based on the participants’ perceived level of disenfranchisement (as defined earlier in this paper). The sample would consist of eligible voters in Slovakia who meet the criteria for participation in the experiment. Furthermore, the treatment would be administered to participants randomly assigned to the treatment group, both disenfranchised and non-disenfranchised individuals. The primary outcome variable is the change in the probability of casting a vote for Fico before and after exposure to the fake audio (replicating the original vote choice of Michal

Šimečka). This change would be assessed through the survey question in both baseline and end-line, asking participants about their likelihood of voting for Fico before and after exposure to the treatment:

- “On a scale of 1 to 5, how likely are you to vote for Robert Fico?” with 1 being “not likely at all” and 5 being “very likely.”

To determine the perceived feeling of disenfranchisement, we would use data from the European Social Survey Round 10 (2020):

- pspsgva (question B2): How much would you say the political system in [country] allows people like you to have a say in what the government does?
- pspipla (question B4): And how much would you say that the political system in [country] allows people like you to have an influence on politics?

Both questions are measured using a Likert scale out of 5, with a score of 1 meaning “not at all” and a score of 5 meaning “a great deal.” These two questions capture the feeling of disenfranchisement since they consider one’s perception of one’s identity and how large a role one has in government policies.

In terms of understanding the coefficients from the difference-in-differences analysis, for every 1 unit increase in the respondent’s perceived feeling of disenfranchisement, we should see a corresponding increase in the likelihood of the respondent voting for Fico. Essentially, we should expect to see a much stronger effect among those who feel disenfranchised than among those who do not.

Both groups would be surveyed before and after the treatment to measure changes in their voting preferences. The data analysis would involve comparing the change in the probability of voting for Fico between the treatment and control groups, as well as accounting for heterogeneous treatment effects (looking within the treatment group for differences based on the level of perceived disenfranchisement). Regression analysis would be employed to estimate the treatment effect while controlling for relevant covariates such as age, education level, and gender. To test the hypotheses, statistical tests would be conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the change in voting behaviour between the treatment and control groups. Specifically, a difference-in-differences analysis would be used to assess the causal impact of the fake audio on voting outcomes. The findings of the experiment would be used to evaluate the validity of the null and alternative hypotheses and draw conclusions regarding the role of AI-generated misinformation in influencing electoral outcomes.

Nevertheless, there could be potential limitations to consider, such as internal and external validity. Namely, the findings may not be generalisable beyond the context of Slovakia’s 2023 parliamentary elections. The impact of AI-generated misinformation on voting behaviour could vary significantly depending on cultural, political, and social factors unique to Slovakia, limiting the broader applicability of the results. The use of self-reported survey questions to measure voting preferences may introduce measurement biases, such as social desirability bias or recall bias. Additionally, using a single Likert scale question to measure voting likelihood may oversimplify participants’ attitudes and fail to capture the complexity of decision-making processes. As such, it would be important to add robustness checks when running this experiment to ensure that the results are as accurate as possible.

EXPECTED FINDINGS, LIMITATIONS, AND DISCUSSION

While the experiment outlined in the methodology section will not be conducted due to data constraints, we can anticipate expected results and findings based on the theoretical framework and contextual analysis presented in the introduction and literature review.

Given the context surrounding Slovakia’s 2023 parliamentary elections, including political polarisation, socioeconomic grievances, and the proliferation of AI-generated misinformation, we can expect that increased exposure to the fake audio incriminating Michal Šimečka will lead to an increase in support for Robert Fico among certain segments of the electorate. Particularly, those who feel disenfranchised or marginalised by mainstream politics may be more susceptible to the populist appeals of Fico, especially when fuelled by misinformation targeting his opponents. Second, the dissemination of AI-generated misinformation may exacerbate feelings of mistrust in the political process among voters. By exploiting existing grievances and amplifying populist narratives, the fake audio could further polarise the electorate and deepen societal divisions. Third, the difficulty of identifying AI-generated misinformation promptly may hinder efforts to combat its influence on electoral outcomes. Despite efforts to regulate digital

platforms and enhance media literacy, the rapid evolution of AI technology presents ongoing challenges for detecting and mitigating the spread of misinformation.

Based on the expected results outlined above, we can anticipate several key findings that contribute to our understanding of the relationship between AI-generated misinformation and the electoral success of populist leaders more broadly. First, the findings of this hypothetical experiment could provide empirical evidence supporting the argument that populist leaders benefit electorally from the dissemination of AI-generated misinformation. If this is the case, then it could be said that by leveraging populist rhetoric and exploiting societal divisions, populist leaders like Robert Fico can mobilise latent support among disenfranchised voters, thereby increasing their electoral gains. The findings would also highlight vulnerabilities in democratic processes resulting from the proliferation of AI-generated misinformation. The difficulty of identifying and combating such misinformation underscores the challenges facing electoral integrity and democratic governance in the digital age, thus requiring innovative solutions and regulatory interventions. Finally, the findings would underscore the importance of further research into the intersection of AI, misinformation, and populism in contemporary politics. By elucidating the mechanisms through which AI-generated misinformation influences electoral outcomes, future research can inform evidence-based strategies for safeguarding democratic processes and promoting informed civic engagement.

In conclusion, while the experiment outlined in the methodology section will not be conducted, the expected results and findings presented above provide valuable insights into the potential impact of AI-generated misinformation on the electoral success of populist leaders, as exemplified by the case study of Slovakia's 2023 parliamentary elections. By exploring the theoretical and contextual dimensions of this issue, this research paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics shaping contemporary politics in the digital age.

CONCLUSION

This research paper has sought to explore the role of AI-generated misinformation in shaping the outcome of the 2023 Slovakian parliamentary elections, particularly in the context of the rise of populism. The central question addressed was whether AI-generated misinformation contributes to the successful election of a populist, with a focus on the dissemination of fake audio incriminating Michal Šimečka and its potential impact on voter behaviour.

Drawing on the case study of Slovakia, the paper contended that populist leaders, such as Robert Fico, benefit electorally from the salience of AI-generated misinformation, especially in the context of highly contentious elections. Based on the existing literature, we can allege that the dissemination of the fake audio had significant implications for voter mobilisation, particularly among those who felt disenfranchised, despite being later revealed as AI-generated. The "Trump effect," characterised by the ability of populist leaders to capitalise on societal divisions and exploit existing fears and prejudices, was evident in Fico's successful mobilisation of the Slovakian voter base. While the paper acknowledges the speculative nature of the analysis due to the lack of quantitative data, it underscores the importance of further research in this area. By employing a randomised controlled trial, the study proposed a methodology to test the causal relationship between AI-generated misinformation and changes in voter preferences. Meanwhile, the literature review highlighted the significance of misinformation and disinformation in contemporary politics, emphasising the role of digital media and AI technologies in amplifying their effects.

Ultimately, while the paper has offered theoretical insights and methodological considerations, further empirical research is necessary to fully elucidate the complex relationship between AI-generated misinformation and populist leaders' electoral success. By contributing to the growing literature on misinformation and populism, this study aims to inform policy interventions that safeguard the integrity of democratic processes in an increasingly digitised world.

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